

In-service English teachers' motivations in the Indonesian teacher profession education program

Tri Wintolo Apoko¹, Bambang Yudi Cahyono²

¹Department of English Education, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka, Jakarta, Indonesia

²Department of English, Faculty of Letters, Universitas Negeri Malang, Malang, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 31, 2023

Revised Dec 28, 2023

Accepted Jan 21, 2024

Keywords:

Extrinsic motivation

In-service English teachers

Intrinsic motivation

Motivation

Teaching profession

ABSTRACT

To be certified as professional English teachers, Indonesian teachers must complete the teacher profession education program (TPEP) offered by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia. Due to a lack of discussion and research on the motivation of in-service English teachers participating in the TPEP, this study explored the TPEP-related motivation of in-service English teachers. There were 80 in-service English teachers who joined the TPEP at a reputable private university in Indonesia participated in this mixed-method study. A survey questionnaire was distributed to the in-service teachers to know their motivation regarding the TPEP. The findings indicated that the majority of the in-service English teachers were highly motivated to participate in the TPEP. They also thought that TPEP was beneficial for teachers as it enhanced their knowledge and skills in teaching. Through the TPEP they learned to use innovative strategies to teach English such as project-based learning and problem-based learning. This implies that more in-service English teachers should be encouraged to join TPEP to develop their competencies.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Tri Wintolo Apoko

Department of English Education, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education,
Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka

Tanah Merdeka Street, Kampung Rambutan, 13830 East Jakarta, Indonesia

Email: triwin_apoko@uhamka.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

English teachers play a significant role in enhancing the standard of English for students of all levels [1]. There are personal, pedagogical, professional, and social competencies that teachers should have [2]–[4], and these should all complement one another. Teachers should be able to construct effective lesson plans, create learning materials, and participate in English teacher forums, seminars, workshops, and training programs for English teachers in order to fulfil and develop these competencies. According to Act No. 14/2005 on teachers and lecturers in Indonesia, teachers are required to participate in the teacher profession education program (TPEP) in order to be qualified as professionals [5]. The TPEP was created by the Indonesian government's Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology to certify teachers and improve the educational quality of both public and private schools throughout Indonesia. Since 2018, a few public and private universities in Indonesia have been assigned to manage the certification of in-service English teachers through TPEP.

In 2018 and 2019, selected in-service English teachers took part in the TPEP for one semester using a blended learning approach. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the TPEP was delivered entirely

online, in both synchronous and asynchronous modes. The program offered a variety of activities via an online learning management system, including reading and analyzing the materials, participating in discussion forums, watching videos, completing assigned tasks, as well as accessing connections for online meetings. As the learning activities were time-consuming, the in-service English teachers had to actively participate in each session to fulfil their attendance requirements and the instructors' expectations. Although this research concerns the topic of in-service English teachers' motivation regarding the TPEP, it is believed that this program has a positive impact and contributes to teachers' professional development (PD). In-service English teachers should therefore perform their teaching duties better after participating in the TPEP. They should also increase their teaching capacity through their interactions with fellow English teachers.

Teachers of English should practice speaking English as well as apply appropriate teaching strategies. Some English teachers find it challenging to teach English to their students in a formal setting; however, many of them can implement instructional strategies, employ instructional materials, effectively use spoken English to communicate, and create their own plans for delivering their lessons. The TPEP is intended to help English teachers overcome their challenges in developing their capabilities. Although many in-service English teachers join the TPEP, not all of them complete all the tasks and earn a professional teacher certificate in teaching English. While some of them were successful in the examination on teaching performance (ETP) and the examination on knowledge (EK), others failed and had to retake the exams in the following season. Failure to complete the TPEP might be a psychological factor that affects the in-service English teachers' well-being as professional teachers. Therefore, examining in-service English teachers' intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in relation to the TPEP is important as motivation is considered to be one of the driving forces that determines success in the program.

Motivation is a personal attribute that drives the process of carrying out particular behaviors. Based on the source of the drive, motivation can be divided into two kinds: intrinsic and extrinsic [6]–[8]. Intrinsic motivation is the desire to engage in a certain activity based on one's own needs, interests, curiosity, and enjoyment [7], [9]–[11]. In contrast, extrinsic motivation is derived from external sources, such as the anticipation of a reward (e.g. cash, prizes, or grades) or escape from a punishment that has nothing to do with the work at hand [9], [11]. In other words, learner motivation refers to one's desire to complete a learning objective while taking into account personal elements including wants, interests, curiosity, and enjoyment in addition to a desire to receive rewards and avoid punishments [12]. Related to the context of in-service English teachers as the learners in the TPEP, it is important to understand their specific motivations—both intrinsic and extrinsic—for participating in the program.

Only a small number of studies have examined in-service English teachers' participation in the TPEP. Most of this research has focused on the results of the teachers' training program and on continuous PD, including studies on teacher training to overcome problems in primary schools during the COVID-19 pandemic [13]; studies on a teacher training program about teachers' family-engagement practices, knowledge, and attitudes, which included preservice teachers, in-service teachers, and professionals [14]; studies on teacher PD through online and blended learning (OBL) [15]; and studies on teacher motivation for PD [16]. Therefore, the current study aims to examine Indonesian in-service English teachers' motivations concerning the TPEP. To achieve this objective, three research questions are put forward as: i) what are in-service English teachers' motivations regarding the TPEP?; ii) what are the benefits of the TPEP for in-service English teachers?; and iii) what aspects of the TPEP did teachers implement in their English teaching practices after they became professional English teachers?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design and participants

This research followed a mixed-methods design by investigating both quantitative and qualitative data [17]. The quantitative data came in the form of an online survey on the in-service English teachers' motivations on TPEP. The qualitative data came through deeper descriptive information obtained from several selected participants' interviews. The participants were 80 in-service English teachers in Indonesia who joined a TPEP conducted by a reputable private university in Jakarta, which was appointed by the Directorate General of Higher Education for the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia. The researchers selected the size of the participants that is typical based on the past studies [17]. Participants volunteered to participate in this research by responding to a survey questionnaire. Before they responded to the survey, participants were informed about the purpose of the study. They were also informed that their participation was voluntary, and the information that they gave in the survey would be treated confidentially and used only for the purpose of the research. The demographic information of the participants is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic information of the participants

Categories	Sub-categories	Number of participants N=80	Percentage (%)	Total (%)		
Gender	Female	65	81	100		
	Male	15	19			
Age	25–30 years old	10	13	100		
	31–35 years old	22	27			
	36–40 years old	31	39			
	40–45 years old	13	16			
	>45 years old	4	5			
Provinces/Islands of origins	Jakarta	15	18	100		
	Banten	18	22			
	West Java	12	15			
	Centra Java	3	4			
	East Java	1	1			
	Sumatera Island	16	20			
	Kalimantan and Sulawesi Islands	4	5			
	Bali	2	3			
	West Nusa Tenggara	2	3			
	East Nusa Tenggara	3	4			
	Papua	4	5			
	Educational level of teaching English	Elementary school	5		6	100
		Junior high school	43		54	
Senior high school		15	19			
Vocational high school		17	21			
Length of teaching experience	<5 years	3	4	100		
	5–8 years	19	24			
	9–12 years	24	30			
	13–15 years	26	32			
	>15 years	8	10			
Recent educational background	Bachelor of Education	64	80	100		
	Other Bachelor Degree	4	5			
	Master of Education	11	14			
	Other Master Degree	1	1			

As shown in Table 1, there were more female English teachers (81%) than males (19%). Their ages ranged between 25–45 years old; of these, 39% ranged between 36–40 years old. The participants were from various provinces and islands although the number of participants from the provinces of Java Island (61.25%) surpassed those from other islands (38.75%). Most of the teachers (54%) were teaching in junior high schools, while the others were teaching in elementary, senior high, and vocational high schools (46%). Participants had various levels of teaching experience: less than 5 years (4%); 5–8 years (24%); 9–12 years (30%); 13–15 years (33%); and more than 15 years (10%). Most of the participants had earned a Bachelor of Education (80%), while some of them had completed their Master of Education degree (14%).

2.2. Data collection and data analysis

To answer the first research question, an online survey questionnaire using Google Forms was distributed to the in-service English teachers. The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part consisted of six items regarding demographic information, and the second part surveyed the teachers' motivations for participating in the TPEP through 19 items presented using a Likert-type scale commonly known as a summated rating scale [18]. Originally, there were 24 items in the second part of the survey questionnaire. However, based on the item analysis of the responses of participants in a pilot study, only 19 items were considered valid, with a reliability coefficient score of 0.895, which is considered to be very high. Each of the questionnaire items contained five response options: strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1) for positive statements; or strongly disagree (5), disagree (4), neutral (3), agree (2), and strongly agree (1) for negative statements. The questions concerned the two types of motivation. The first type, intrinsic motivation, has four indicators: needs, interests, curiosity, and enjoyment. The second type, extrinsic motivation, also has four indicators: rewards, punishments, compliance, and reactance. Each of the indicators for the types of motivations had one to three items in the survey. The detailed specifications of the questions that were selected following the pilot study are displayed in Table 2.

Apart from the survey questionnaire, which was used to answer the first research question, a semi-structured interview was also used to collect the data from nine selected participants. The nine participants were labelled as P19, P24, P26, P43, P52, P65, P67, P69, and P73. They were asked to answer three questions. The first question further explored the in-service English teachers' motivations for participating in the TPEP mentioned in the survey questionnaire. The second and third questions focused on the benefits of the TPEP and the implementation of the program's concepts by in-service English teachers' after they were

certified as professional English teachers. As this research used a mixed-methods design, the questionnaire data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. At the same time, the interview data were analyzed using three steps: reducing data, displaying data, and concluding data [19]. In light of the three research questions, the results of the two data analyses are presented and discussed next section.

Table 2. The specification of motivation on TPEP after the tryout

No	Types of motivation	Indicators	Item number	Amount
1	Intrinsic motivation	Needs	1, 2, 3	3
		Interests	4, 5, 6	3
		Curiosity	7	1
		Enjoyment	8, 9, 10	3
2	Extrinsic motivation	Rewards	11, 12	2
		Punishment	13, 14, 15	3
		Compliance	16, 17	2
		Reactance	18, 19	2
Total				19

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. In-service English teachers' motivations regarding the teacher profession education program

The results of the analysis of the quantitative data on in-service English teachers' motivations are presented based on the indicators of each type of motivation, namely needs, interest, curiosity, enjoyment (intrinsic motivations), rewards, punishment, compliance, and reactance (extrinsic motivations). The data are presented in terms of the percentages of the responses for the five options, the means of the value, and the standard deviation (SD). The analysis focuses on the two most favorable responses (strongly agree and agree for positive items and strongly disagree and disagree for negative items).

3.1.1. Needs

The results of the data analysis on the in-service English teachers' need to participate in the TPEP are presented in Table 3. The table shows that most in-service English teachers (98%) have a high need to participate in the TPEP as it is required to be a professional teacher of English. This finding is in line with one study stating that teachers may have more favorable attitudes towards taking part in conferences, workshops, and forums on topics related to current research. It was also said that in order to better prepare successful teachers for the realities of the classroom on a daily basis, teacher trainers—including those working in the Iranian educational system—are encouraged to re-plan their PD programs to meet the needs of the teachers in their particular educational context [20], including the least qualified [21].

Another result from the survey indicated that in-service English teachers believed that taking part in the TPEP could make them more knowledgeable and skillful at teaching. Beyond their own knowledge, abilities, dispositions, and goals, teachers' practices are also influenced by their colleagues, professional networks, institutional policies, and national discourses [22]. However, it was found that 1% of them reported having no improvement in their teaching skill after joining TPEP. The other question dealing with their need to join the TPEP found that 88% of the participants felt that it is necessary to engage in the TPEP activities to advance their teaching careers. In long-term training programs, teachers create possibilities for networking and community building and advance their careers [23]. To help support these efforts, organizational policies should offer assistance to teachers at different phases of their career [24].

Table 3. In-service English teachers' needs on TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
1	I needed to join TPEP to be a professional teacher.	1	0	1	33	65	4.600	0.648
2	Participating TPEP increased my knowledge and teaching skills.	1	0	0	28	71	4.675	0.612
3	To be involved in TPEP was not necessary for my teaching career.	39	49	8	4	1	4.200	0.833

3.1.2. Personal interest

The in-service English teachers' interests in the TPEP are presented in Table 4. The table shows that all the in-service English teachers (100%) were interested in joining all of the activities during the TPEP. This finding is supported by a study in Finland which demonstrated that teacher educators encountered a range of issues at work, initially relating to their role as newly qualified teachers and later with teaching-related issues such as severe workloads [20]. The current study also found that nearly all teachers (98%) paid

attention to their instructors' lessons about teacher professionalism. This idea is strengthened with an argument stating that one experienced teacher who joined an in-service teacher program was thinking about how important listening is to developing and executing in-service programs [21]. The current study also found that 91% of the participants did not stop doing some assignments when they found TPEP activities to be challenging. Thus, teachers desired to improve their pedagogical knowledge in various domains, including instructional techniques, curriculum, and assessment. One of the biggest obstacles for the majority of teachers was specifically teaching through inquiry [22].

Table 4. In-service English teachers' interests on TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
4	I was interested in taking part in all the activities in the TPEP.	0	0	0	55	45	4.45	0.501
5	I paid attention to what my instructors taught me about how to be a professional teacher.	2	0	0	49	49	4.413	0.741
6	When I found the TPEP activities difficult, I stopped doing some of my tasks.	35	56	5	3	1	4.213	0.758

3.1.3. Curiosity

The in-service English teachers' curiosity in the TPEP is presented in Table 5. As it is seen in the table, most in-service English teachers (94%) were curious about reading the materials prior to discussions with the instructors because of their interest in the TPEP. In this case, they were acting actively as the materials were very important for them to understand and participate. This result reflects the understanding that teachers who actively participate in their own education take greater responsibility for it, which aids their PD [23]. The eagerness to engage in the reading materials also demonstrates self-esteem, accountability, and sense of success [24].

Table 5. In-service English teachers' curiosity in the TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
7	I was curious to read some materials before having discussions with my instructors.	0	1	5	68	26	4.188	0.576

3.1.4. Enjoyment

The in-service English teachers' enjoyment of the TPEP is presented in Table 6. Based on the results of this study as shown in Table 6, 99% of participants found it enjoyable to participate in the TPEP, where they created some learning tools and subsequently used them in their teaching activities. They enjoyed the TPEP, much like other professionals who participated in development activities, such as seminars, workshops, conferences, lectures, and exhibitions that were intended to enhance employees in a school from the point of first employment through retirement [25].

Additionally, the in-service English teachers enjoyed the exercises because they were guided by the instructors, and what they did in the TPEP was not difficult for them (95%). However, one study proposed that there were significant difficulties for in-service teachers in providing a theoretical foundation for their comments, and they required greater mentoring support [26]. Although this TPEP was implemented online, 88% of the teachers reported that they were predominantly not bored with the materials shared by the instructors. Thus, most of the teachers had positive views on using technology for learning during the TPEP. In fact, the TPEP offered teachers strategies and techniques for successfully integrating information and communication technology (ICT) in the classroom [27].

Table 6. In-service English teachers' enjoyment of the TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
8	I enjoyed the activities in the TPEP such as producing a set of learning tools and doing teaching performance practice.	0	0	1	53	46	4.450	0.525
9	Participating in the TPEP was not easy for me, so I did not like TPEP activities.	39	56	5	0	0	4.338	0.572
10	I was bored with the materials shared by the instructors during online learning.	33	55	10	3	0	4.175	0.708

3.1.5. Rewards

The results of the data analysis on the in-service English teachers' motivation due to rewards in the TPEP are presented in Table 7. The table reveals that even when participants received no praise for their work from their TPEP instructors, 86% of them said they were still doing their best. However, 5% said that they would not do their best, and 9% of them were neutral. Most of them did their best as they thought that they had to be successful in the TPEP. These results are in accordance with a recent study that discovered that participants were inspired by achievement, efficient working conditions, pupils' eagerness for learning, and becoming more independent [28]. In addition, the current study found that most English teachers continued to improve their teaching practices even when they had no rewards from their instructors (93%). The current study again showed that rewards were not particularly influential for in-service English teachers, suggesting that offering rewards may not have the desired effects. Therefore, findings from neuroscientific, sociological, and educational studies should be considered if rewards are to be used [29].

Table 7. The in-service English teachers' motivation through rewards in the TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
11	Even though my instructors did not appreciate my assignments, I was still doing my best.	1	4	9	55	31	4.113	0.811
12	I would not improve my teaching skills if I had no rewards from my instructors.	35	58	2	3	2	4.200	0.818

3.1.6. Punishment

The in-service English teachers' motivation due to punishment is presented in Table 8. The table indicates that the majority of in-service English teachers (97%) responded favorably towards errors in their lesson plans, which reflects the idea of punishment as one of the extrinsic motivators. Nearly all teachers would alter the lesson plan in this situation. Additionally, if they received lower grades from the instructors, they would continue to make an effort (94%). Lastly, participants reported that they would not detest the TPEP if they failed in the teaching performance assessment (4%). Thus, as shown in recent studies, using punishments effectively could have a significant positive impact on one's motivation and performance [30]. For example, when speaking sanctions were used by teachers to alter learner behavior and instill fear, students would not repeat their errors while learning English [31].

Table 8. The in-service English teachers' motivation because of punishment in the TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
13	If my lesson plan contained mistakes, I would revise them right away.	0	1	2	54	43	4.375	0.603
14	After I got lower grades, I was not willing to do other assignments.	31	63	5	1	0	4.238	0.601
15	If I did not pass my teaching exam, I would be upset and hate the TPEP.	40	51	5	3	1	4.263	0.775

3.1.7. Compliance

The in-service English teachers' motivation through compliance during the TPEP is presented in Table 9. The table shows that the majority of in-service English teachers practiced teaching more effectively by applying their teaching knowledge (99%). In addition, all of the participants reported that they would comply with the instructors' requests to create innovative learning models (100%). In line with these results, compliance is believed to be facilitated by a mix of normative and social reasons, as well as an understanding of the rules and the ability to follow them. This study advanced knowledge of the variables influencing compliance with social and environmental regulations [32]. Another study found that there were positive and negative drivers of compliance with social and environmental regulations. It was said that positive intentions and a sense of duty to comply were the sources of affirmative motives, and this was closely related to the current study [33].

Table 9. The in-service English teachers' motivation through compliance in the TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
16	I used my teaching knowledge to teach better.	1	0	0	45	54	4.500	0.636
17	I would do what my instructors asked to design innovative learning models better.	0	0	0	61	39	4.388	0.490

3.1.8. Reactance

The in-service English teachers' motivation through reactance on the TPEP is presented in Table 10. The results from Table 10 show that, despite their peers telling them that they were not good at teaching, the majority of the participants would continue to practice teaching English more effectively (95%). Furthermore, despite an instructor's threats to deduct points for an ineffective teaching performance, the participants would continue to participate in the activity (97%). The current study is supported by one relevant study which stated that when reacting, participants were more likely to pursue personal endeavors (personal-abstract) than security-related (personal-concrete) activities. In addition, the findings implied that people reacted to threats in different ways, largely depending on their affective states and motivational orientations: anxiety was linked to security, approach-state to action (both social and personal), reactance to derogation of the system, and disregard for security, while loneliness was linked to inaction [34].

Table 10. The in-service English teachers' motivation of the reactance on TPEP

No	Questionnaire items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
18	If my classmate told me that I was not good at teaching, I would keep practicing how to teach English better.	1	1	1	52	45	4.375	0.700
19	If my instructors threatened me to give a lower score for my teaching performance, I would not participate anymore.	36	61	1	1	1	4.288	0.679

3.1.9. Findings from the interviews on the in-service English teachers' motivation during the TPEP

From the interviews with a few selected in-service English teachers, it was possible to generate additional findings about the participants' motivations during the TPEP. One participant (P24) who is a female English teacher at a senior high school in Sulawesi Island and has been teaching for thirteen years claimed to have one reason to participate in the TPEP. She stated, "*Of course I will get more salary.*" This idea is relevant to this study since it has been demonstrated that inadequate continuous PD training allowances and poor working conditions, including low pay and accommodations for teachers, make it difficult for teachers to properly use what they have learned in continuous PD training in the classroom [35]. In addition, teachers have complained that their needs were not met to their standards [36], [37].

Another cause for motivation was mentioned by a participant (P26) who is a male English teacher in a junior high school in Sumatera Island and has been teaching for six years. He stated that he was motivated "*to learn how to be a good teacher, extend knowledge about teaching and how to use innovative learning models in the classroom, and so on.*" Likewise, another participant (P43) who has been teaching English in junior high school in West Java for three years also said, "*because I want to improve my teaching skill and give my best to my students, and I want to learn how to be a professional teacher,*" and an English female teacher (P65) who had four years of junior high school teaching experience in Depok, West Java remarked, "*I joined TPEP to be a professional teacher and to get more knowledge and skills in teaching.*" Finally, a participant (P67) who is a female English teacher in an elementary school located in Jakarta and has been teaching for four years said she desired "*to improve my skill in teaching learning process and deliver best knowledge with some methods, so students can get more fun experiences in learning.*" From these responses, it seems that teachers recognize that they need to possess a specific set of knowledge, abilities, and ideals in order to fulfil their duties and responsibilities with passion [38]. Collaboration with colleagues for the purpose of enhancing a lesson or learning activities could help to improve teaching abilities and knowledge [39].

Another participant (P69), a female English teacher who has been working in a junior high school in East Java for 10 years stated, "*Joining TPEP is a wonderful experience for me because I never expected before. I had to study many things not only on my learning tools to teach but also to learn anything about technology.*" Thus, ongoing PD programs can help teachers create confidence in their capacity to modify their instruction and accommodate technological advancements in the classroom [40].

3.2. The benefits of teacher profession education program

From the interview results, all the in-service English teachers presented convincing reasons for the benefits of the TPEP. As an illustration, they might hone their abilities and knowledge, particularly with regard to creating better learning models, utilizing ICT technologies to give engaging and creative instruction, and utilizing English in their instruction. These results are comparable to another study indicating that the training program was well-received by the teachers who took part in it, and they distinguished themselves significantly from the control group in terms of their capacity for stress management and the prevention of burnout, as well as their proficiency with ICT and the integration of emotional intelligence (EI) into the classroom [13].

In contrast, in one teacher training program in China, according to precise estimations, both teacher and student results were not improved after one year of PD and related interventions [41]. A thorough study

of the causal chain revealed that the delivery of PD, according to the teachers' beliefs, was too formulaic and passive and that the content was too theoretical [41]. Another relevant study on PD programs showed that programs that had a specific subject focus, related participation to career incentives, involved lesson enactment in the training, and included initial face-to-face training tended to exhibit higher student learning improvements [42]. The following are some of the ideas that teachers expressed during the interviews.

- P19: *"I got a lot of experiences after having this program. I met good teachers, lecturers, and many more. And, the most important thing is that I got knowledge about how to be a professional teacher."*
- P26: *"I met many awesome teachers with innovative learning models that I could imitate for my classroom to make my students study better and enjoy English in class. Then, I knew how to make a set of learning tools that suit with my students' needs in class."*
- P43: *"There are many things that I get from this program, such as new experience that are full of struggles, new teacher friends and useful knowledge that I can apply in my classroom."*
- P52: *"I've got more experiences and new skills to make a set of planning, actualizing and evaluating learning activities."*
- P65: *"I got more skills in teaching English and knowledge, especially about lesson plans, assessment and innovative learning."*
- P67: *"I've got a lot of information and strategies to make my class and students more interested in learning."*
- P69: *"After I joined the program, I got many things such as how to design a better lesson plan based on my student characteristics, and I forced my brain to learn about technology in my teaching and learning process, and it made me realize that my students were more joyful, and I could see their cheerful faces when they joined my class."*

3.3. The results of the TPEP

Most in-service English teachers considered the TPEP to be effective, especially in that they learned to implement innovative learning models such as problem-based learning and project-based learning. In addition, they learned how to design better lesson plans for their own instruction and to use interesting learning media based on technology. To support these views, the interviewees shared what they have done after completing the TPEP.

- P19: *"I shared my knowledge to the other teachers, and they were happy and always support my teaching activities."*
- P24: *"I tried to do my best in teaching in my class and make good lesson plans based on my students' situation and school environment."*
- P26: *"I implemented some learning models in my classes such as problem-based learning and project-based learning to make students enjoy the English lesson."*
- P43: *"I've implemented the way to make a good and complete lesson plan using problem-based learning and project-based learning in my classroom and to make students as the center of learning."*
- P52: *"First, I tried to make better lesson plans than those I made before I joined TPEP. Second, I tried to apply the lesson plans on my teaching activity in the class."*
- P65: *"I asked my students to sing a song together or do small exercises in the pre-activity for fun activity and make sure the students were ready. In the main activities, I tried to make learning activities more innovative by using various media such as videos, audio, songs, worksheet, and games. For the closing, there was a pair assessment. In this case, every student gave a score to other students' performance, and it could make the students more active."*
- P67: *"I joined discussions in a group or individually. I also gave stimulus for students to explore the lesson by their own characteristics."*
- P69: *"When I completed this program in 2021, I started to use interactive power point that included videos in my learning activities to make an interesting lesson. I was also active to share experience that I got from this program, especially from my favorite instructor on how to design the best lesson plan to other teachers in my school."*
- P73: *"I tried to use some kinds of media, give a fun and meaningful learning, and use the two learning models such as problem-based learning and project-based learning. I also learned some learning applications by joining webinars."*

The results are supported by some relevant studies. In the 21st century, teachers should be able to adapt their instructions with the use of technology [43]. Moreover, teachers must be equipped with the appropriate 21st-century skills, including reading, learning, and creativity, information, media, and technology, as well as life and career skills [44]. Therefore, schools at any level of education require teachers with new competencies. It is essential to have teachers who can continuously learn new skills, particularly those related to interpersonal and relational skills in today's classrooms. As a result, social-emotional skills and effective classroom management go hand in hand as a teacher develops professionally [45]. What has been implemented by in-service English teachers seems impressive. The teachers encourage their students to feel joyful in the classroom as they provide some songs to sing and learning through videos, audio, and some other digital media to make their lessons attractive. Through the TPEP, teacher educators gain skills to be at the top of their field [46]. At the very least, these participants of the TPEP were satisfied with the program and disseminated what they learned and practiced to other English teachers at their own schools.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study has explored in-service English teachers' motivations during a TPEP, their thoughts about the benefits of the TPEP program, and what they implemented after they became certified as professional teachers. It is revealed that in-service English teachers had strong motivations to join the TPEP, as explained in the findings and discussion section. Their motivations—both intrinsic and extrinsic—tend to be positive as they have keen interests and a strong sense of curiosity to learn more about how to teach well. They thought that the TPEP would help them become more skilled at creating lesson plans, implementing cutting-edge teaching strategies, and using technology-based learning materials and media. In fact, they learned to use problem-based learning and project-based learning to teach English successfully while implementing their own skills and knowledge. Following these findings, it is advised that in-service English teachers continue to develop both their teaching skills and their English proficiency in order to provide an enjoyable and conducive environment for students during the teaching and learning process.

This study has examined in-service English teachers with varying levels of education from various parts of Indonesia, including all of the provinces on Java, Sumatra, Kalimantan, and Sulawesi Islands, Bali, Nusa Tenggara, and the provinces in Papua. However, there are still some limitations, such as the small number of participants who participated in filling out the survey questionnaire. In addition, time constraints could be the other limitation to conduct this study. Therefore, future research might involve larger sample of participants from various provinces. Future research might also focus on comparing motivations of the participants' motivations in joining the TPEP based on their geographical as well as their educational background.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the in-service English teachers who joined the TPEP at the University of Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka from Batch 2019 to Batch 2022 and volunteered to take part in this study by responding to the questionnaire. The authors would also like to express their gratitude to the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University of Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka, Jakarta, for the support and permission to this study. A great appreciation is delivered to the Unit for Scientific Publication Development of University of Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka for funding this research and for being the sponsor in the publication.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Zhumash, A. Zhumabaeva, S. Nurgaliyeva, G. Saduakas, L. A. Lebedeva, and S. B. Zhoraeva, "Professional teaching competence in preservice primary school teachers: structure, criteria and levels," *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 261–271, 2021, doi: 10.18844/wjet.v13i2.5699.
- [2] B. Fauth *et al.*, "The effects of teacher competence on student outcomes in elementary science education: the mediating role of teaching quality," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 86, p. 102882, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2019.102882.
- [3] U. Rusilowati and W. Wahyudi, "The significance of educator certification in developing pedagogy, personality, social and professional competencies," in *2nd Social and Humaniora Research Symposium (SoRes 2019)*, 2020, pp. 446–451, doi: 10.2991/assehr.k.200225.095.
- [4] F. A. Albrahim, "Online teaching skills and competencies," *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology (TOJET)*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 9–20, 2020.
- [5] S. P. Kawuryan, S. A. Sayuti, and S. I. A. Dwiningrum, "Teachers quality and educational equality achievements in Indonesia," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 811–830, 2021, doi: 10.29333/iji.2021.14245a.
- [6] H. D. Brown, *Principles of language learning and teaching*, 6th ed. Pearson Education, 2014.
- [7] J. Howard, M. Gagné, A. J. S. Morin, and A. van den Broeck, "Motivation profiles at work: a self-determination theory approach," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 95, pp. 74–89, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2016.07.004.

- [8] C. F. Ng and P. K. Ng, "A review of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations of ESL learners," *International Journal of Languages, Literature and Linguistics*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 98–105, 2015, doi: 10.7763/IJLL.2015.V1.20.
- [9] C. Marsh, *Becoming a teacher: knowledge, skills and issues*, 5th ed. NSW: Pearson, 2010.
- [10] R. L. Oxford and D. Bolaños-Sánchez, "A tale of two learners: discovering mentoring, motivation, emotions, engagement, and perseverance," in *New directions in language learning psychology*, C. Gkonou, D. Tatzl, and S. Mercer, Eds. London: Springer, 2016, pp. 113–134.
- [11] J. C. Richards and W. A. Renandya, "Teaching listening," in *Methodology in language teaching*, 1st ed., Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002, pp. 235–237.
- [12] T. W. Apoko and S. Warni, "An investigation of EFL preservice teachers' attitudes and motivations in developing a digital learning video," *Jurnal Kependidikan: Jurnal Hasil Penelitian dan Kajian Kepustakaan di Bidang Pendidikan, Pengajaran dan Pembelajaran*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 355–366, 2022, doi: 10.33394/jk.v8i2.4933.
- [13] T. Pozo-Rico, R. Gilar-Corbí, A. Izquierdo, and J.-L. Castejón, "Teacher training can make a difference: tools to overcome the impact of COVID-19 on primary schools. An experimental study," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 22, p. 8633, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17228633.
- [14] T. E. Smith and S. M. Sheridan, "The effects of teacher training on teachers' family-engagement practices, attitudes, and knowledge: a meta-analysis," *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 128–157, 2019, doi: 10.1080/10474412.2018.1460725.
- [15] B. Philipsen, J. Tondeur, N. P. Roblin, S. Vanslambrouck, and C. Zhu, "Improving teacher professional development for online and blended learning: a systematic meta-aggregative review," *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 67, pp. 1145–1174, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11423-019-09645-8.
- [16] D. J. Osman and J. R. Warner, "Measuring teacher motivation: the missing link between professional development and practice," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 92, p. 103064, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2020.103064.
- [17] J. W. Creswell and J. D. Creswell, *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*, 5th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018.
- [18] P. Spector, *Summated rating scale construction*, Newbury Park, CA, USA: SAGE Publications, Inc., 1992.
- [19] M. B. Miles, A. M. Huberman, and J. Saldana, *Qualitative data analysis*, 3rd ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2014.
- [20] K. Maaranen, H. Kynäslähti, R. Byman, R. Jyrhämä, and S. Sintonen, "Teacher education matters: Finnish teacher educators' concerns, beliefs, and values," *European Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 211–227, 2019, doi: 10.1080/02619768.2019.1566317.
- [21] T. J. Cooney and K. Krainer, "Inservice mathematics teacher education: the importance of listening," in *International handbook of mathematics education: part 1*, Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 1996, pp. 1155–1185, doi: 10.1007/978-94-009-1465-0_36.
- [22] M. Zhang, J. Parker, M. J. Koehler, and J. Eberhardt, "Understanding inservice science teachers' needs for professional development," *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 471–496, 2015, doi: 10.1007/s10972-015-9433-4.
- [23] A. Novozhenina and M. M. L. Pinzón, "Impact of a professional development program on EFL teachers' performance," *HOW*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 113–128, 2018, doi: 10.19183/how.25.2.406.
- [24] A. Iliya and L. G. Ifeoma, "Assessment of teacher motivation approaches in the less developed countries," *Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 6, no. 22, pp. 10–17, 2015.
- [25] E. F. Osamwonyi, "In-service education of teachers: overview, problems and the way forward," *Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 7, no. 26, pp. 83–87, 2016.
- [26] Z. S. Genç, "More practice for pre-service teachers and more theory for in-service teachers of English language," *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 232, pp. 677–683, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.10.092.
- [27] N. I. Cetin, "Effects of a teacher professional development program on science teachers' views about using computers in teaching and learning," *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, vol. 11, no. 15, pp. 8026–8039, 2016.
- [28] N. Börü, "The factors affecting teacher-motivation," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 761–776, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.12973/iji.2018.11448a.
- [29] S. Hidi, "Revisiting the role of rewards in motivation and learning: implications of neuroscientific research," *Educational Psychology Review*, vol. 28, pp. 61–93, 2016, doi: 10.1007/s10648-015-9307-5.
- [30] S. A. Sidin, "The application of reward and punishment in teaching adolescents," in *Ninth International Conference on Language and Arts (ICLA 2020)*, 2021, pp. 251–255, doi: 10.2991/assehr.k.210325.045.
- [31] N. Putri and R. Refnaldi, "Rewards and punishments given by the teacher in teaching English as foreign language in Indonesian context," *Journal of English Language Teaching*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 75–85, 2020, doi: 10.24036/jelt.v9i1.107819.
- [32] S. C. Winter and P. J. May, "Motivation for compliance with environmental regulations," *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management: The Journal of the Association for Public Policy Analysis and Management*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 675–698, 2001, doi: 10.1002/pam.1023.
- [33] P. J. May, "Compliance motivations: affirmative and negative bases," *Law & Society Review*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 41–68, 2004, doi: 10.1111/j.0023-9216.2004.03801002.x.
- [34] S. Reiss, V. Franchina, C. Jutzi, R. Willardt, and E. Jonas, "From anxiety to action—experience of threat, emotional states, reactance, and action preferences in the early days of COVID-19 self-isolation in Germany and Austria," *PLoS One*, vol. 15, no. 12, p. e0243193, 2020, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0243193.
- [35] E. S. Meke, "Teacher motivation and implementation of continuing professional development programmes in Malawi," *The Anthropologist*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 107–115, 2013, doi: 10.1080/09720073.2013.11891297.
- [36] F. Gokce, "Assessment of teacher motivation," *School Leadership and Management*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 487–499, 2010, doi: 10.1080/13632434.2010.525228.
- [37] F. T. Gemeda and P. Tynjälä, "Exploring teachers' motivation for teaching and professional development in Ethiopia: voices from the field," *Journal of Studies of Education*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2015, doi: 10.5296/jse.v5i2.7459.
- [38] V. Claudia, "The role of motivation in the development of school teachers' career," *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 180, pp. 1109–1115, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.02.220.
- [39] T. L. Durksen, R. M. Klassen, and L. M. Daniels, "Motivation and collaboration: the keys to a developmental framework for teachers' professional learning," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 67, pp. 53–66, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2017.05.011.
- [40] X. Zhang, W. Admiraal, and N. Saab, "Teachers' motivation to participate in continuous professional development: relationship with factors at the personal and school level," *Journal of Education for Teaching*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 714–731, 2021, doi: 10.1080/02607476.2021.1942804.

- [41] P. Loyalka, A. Popova, G. Li, and Z. Shi, "Does teacher training actually work? Evidence from a large-scale randomized evaluation of a national teacher training program," *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 128–154, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1257/app.20170226.
- [42] A. Popova, D. K. Evans, M. E. Breeding, and V. Arancibia, "Teacher professional development around the world: The gap between evidence and practice," *The World Bank Research Observer*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 107–136, 2022, doi: 10.1596/1813-9450-8572.
- [43] B. Yusuf, "Essential technology skills for 21st-century teacher inclusive strategies," in *Teacher professional knowledge and development for reflective and inclusive practices*, New York: Routledge, 2017, pp. 146–157.
- [44] J. Sulaiman and S. N. Ismail, "Teacher competence and 21st century skills in transformation schools 2025 (TS25)," *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 3536–3544, 2020, doi: 10.13189/ujer.2020.080829.
- [45] M. C. Zaragoza, J. Díaz-Gibson, A. F. Caparrós, and S. L. Solé, "The teacher of the 21st century: professional competencies in Catalonia today," *Educational Studies*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 217–237, 2021, doi: 10.1080/03055698.2019.1686697.
- [46] A. Srinivasacharlu, "Continuing professional development (CPD) of Teacher educators in 21st century," *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 29–33, 2019, doi: 10.34293/education.v7i4.624.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Tri Wintolo Apoko is an Associate Professor in the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. Hamka. He was appointed a lecturer in the university in 2005 and completed his graduate studies for Master and Doctoral Programs in Language Education at Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia. His current research interests focus on writing, curriculum and material development, English teacher professional development, and ICT in ELT. He can be contacted: triwin_apoko@uhamka.ac.id.

Bambang Yudi Cahyono is a Professor in Applied Linguistics at Universitas Negeri Malang, East Java, Indonesia. He earned his M.Pd. (Magister in Education) from 'IKIP Malang' Institute of Teacher Training and Education, Malang, Indonesia, M.A. from Concordia University, Montreal, Canada and Ph.D. from the University of Melbourne, Australia. His research interest includes second language writing, English teacher professional development, and ICT in ELT. He can be contacted at bambang.yudi.fs@um.ac.id.